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In memoriam

Lučka Ažman Momirski (1961 - 2024)

Our dear friend Lučka, an architect and professor of Urban Design at the University of Ljubljana, is present in our lives. Ever since I met her (Maruja, Peruvian anthropologist, ITLA member), at the First International Conference on Terraced Landscapes held in 2010 in Mengzi, Yunnan, China, Lučka's interventions impressed me because they radiated a sincere appreciation and commitment to the skills and wisdom of terraced landscape creators. Her friendly and dialoguing character contributed to establishing a fluid source of mutual synergies, as founder of the ITLA Network Alliance, with many other participants.

In my specific case (Lidia, Canarian geographer from ITLA) and despite the language barrier that separated us, we exchanged ties of work, affection and mutual admiration. I will never forget the first time I saw your spectacular photo gallery of terraced landscapes of your beautiful little country, Slovenia, in that imposing hall with an Inka Stone wall of the municipality of Cusco, just 10 years ago.

Lučka was a landscape architect of exceptional sensitivity, capable of valuing the architectural work, landscapes and territories, as well as the prominence of its builders and caretakers. A tireless worker, she participated in all phases of the organization of the international terrace congresses, from the selection of themes, actions, fieldwork areas, to the scientific work linked to the reception of the works to be presented, to their publication. In the last ten years she has actively contributed to the definition of the editorial line of the themes that were addressed and incorporated in each edition of the international congresses, thus promoting a rich exchange of ideas and practices. She selected articles with her scientific excellence from relevant debates that emerged from the Congresses in Peru (2014), Italy (2016) and the Canary Islands (2019). As editor-in-chief of ITLA's three journals (Journal of Terraced Landscapes JOTL, ITLA Journal and ITLA Art Journal) she was a woman committed to the continuity of this network of actors of many nationalities and professions, linked by the defense of the world's terraced landscapes.

Lučka nurtured a growing network of authors who contributed to giving new meanings to terraced landscapes by overcoming the gaze that focuses on dry stone walls built for functional or aesthetic purposes. The openness of ideas assumed by Lučka in the coordination of the different volumes of ITLA as a virtual publication (see in <http://itla.si>) became a cradle of new pluralistic and multiple forms of knowledge and practices for the transformation of hillsides into gardens of biodiversity, as well as new paths for alternative forms of human life gaining autonomy to rethink and imagine the future.

Dear Lučka, you contributed to laying the foundations of ITLA as a social movement that includes local guardians and activists, university students and professors, children, young people and the elderly, a wide number of professionals and scientists from very diverse disciplines and we are eternally grateful. For us, your life symbolizes fruitful terraced landscapes for future generations.

It's hard for us to think that we won't see you with us visiting new old terraced landscapes. Visits planned to connect with its inhabitants, who are encouraged to continue with their work as custodians of those spaces inherited from our ancestors and from which such good harvests have been obtained throughout their history. Someday we will succeed in declaring and institutionalizing the European Day of Terraced Landscapes and, given its abundant presence on all continents and many of the world's mountainous islands, World Terraced Landscape Day. Until that day comes, there is a lot of research-assessment and dissemination work to continue doing. You're gone so soon, friend. But you will always be with us.

Maruja Salas and Lidia E. Romero Martín (guest editors of the JOTL on Women and Platforms)

Introduction

Recuperating our breath in memory of Lučka

Timmi Tillmann, Deputy Editor of ITLA Publications.

The International Terraced Landscapes Alliance Journal serves as a forum for the activities of the various terraced landscape networks and reflects the experiences of ITLA members and their local or national networks for the revitalisation of terraced landscapes and their custodians in different parts of the world - on all continents. Until now with the direction of Prof. Lucka Azman from Ljubljana University we published 4 numbers (2 volumes) with experiences from Japan, Italy, France, Cyprus and Peru. Our friend and colleague Lucka passed away 2 months ago and together with Dr. Tomaž Berčič we have decided to continue with the 3 ITLA publications: Scientific JOTL, Art Journal and ITLA Journal. On our website we also have published the Proceedings of the 4 International Congresses on Terraced Landscapes in China 2010, Peru 2014, Italy 2016, Canary Islands and Madeira 2019. COVID 19 interrupted our plans for international encounters of ITLA and we still are working on the realisation of the next Congress in Bhutan.

In this section on ITLA as an international alliance of local and regional networks, we have opened a forum for deliberation on the experiences, ideas and concepts of the various networks in the world's terraced lands. We explain the evolution of ITLA as a growing movement of individuals and institutions working to conserve and recover terraced landscapes, support their inhabitants and reaffirm local cultures by promoting the special use of the diversity of products from terraces.

In the coming years, we will continue to reflect on the experiences of ITLA members and their local or national networks to re-enchant terraced landscapes and their guardians in different parts of the world - on all continents. In the ITLA Journal we aim to include articles about our alliance, the governance aspects of a global movement, the activities and events of local and regional networks, the presentation of innovative ways of thinking, acting and feeling, about the head, hands and heart of terraced landscapes and their

custodians and builders. In addition to the ITLA Journal, we continue to send out the ITLA Newsletter to members who contribute to the circular newsletter with their announcements, experiences, publications and events.

Please consider to send in your contributions to our movement. Please read the instructions for authors if you are willing to present your ideas and experiences within our ITLA Journal.

<https://itla.si/itla--instructions-for-authors.html>

Third volume Number 1 2024

This number of the Third Volume of the ITLA Journal means a reset for our editorial work following the guidelines we agreed upon with Lucka after the 4th Congress on Terraced Landscapes on the Canary Islands, where Lucka acted as Scientific Coordinator. We start with an obituary of Lucka Azman written by our guest editors Maruja Salas and Lidia Romero Martin. In recent years we have lost several pivotal members of our ITLA movement: Mourik Bueno de Mesquita (Cusco), Enrico Fontanari (Venice), Heather Peters (Bangkok) and now Lucka Azman (Ljubljana).

The first article by Raimund Rodewald deals with Traditional irrigation: Candidature for Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. After dry stone walls, another infrastructure of terraced landscapes is in the focus of UNESCO: "Traditional Irrigation in Europe - Knowledge, Technique and Organisation" is the title of the current submission of 7 countries from March 2022 for the attention of the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity.

The second article by Sonia Schmid about The terraced landscape of the Terragnolo Valley in Northern Italy, Trentino describes the remains of a terraced landscape and its culture abandoned since World War I. The toponymy of places and oral testimonies help to understand the ancient and recent past of the territory and the new ways of inhabiting the valley. The International Terraced Landscape Festival and Competition, organized by "Sassi e non solo" and held in the Terragnolo Valley since 2017, aims to promote the ancient construction technique. Renato Stedile has given his photos to illustrate the

Figure 1. 5 Walls built during the 8th Dry Stone Wall Festival by the stone masons from Cyprus, Trento, Liguria, Piemonte and Sardegna

Figure 2. After 7 years of Sassie non solo (Not only Rocks) the landscape has been marked with precious stable walls

situation of this mountain valley.

The 8th Dry Stone Wall Contest 2024 can be observed in Youtube with this 25' video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DHgN12aNSqM>

Perspectives

Our next number Vol 3 Nr 2 will be dedicated to the European Days and Festivals: the first one in Vrtovin 2019, where the ITLA Committee joined the whole process and we also met together in Goriska Brda, the wine and cherry region close to the Italian border; and the second events organised in Salamiou, Cyprus with the newly formed ITLA Cyprus network integrated by Vassiliki Petropoulou, Panayoti Panayotou and Sevina Floridou end of October in 2023 and in 2024. We will reproduce the description of the events by the protagonists illustrated with pictures regarding the work with children and youth starting the theme of Terrace Pedagogy.

In 2025 we will develop the preparations for the next Congress in Bhutan about Widening our horizons: Decolonising our minds and concepts with a mountain perspective and the possibilities of a Mediterranean and European Workshop next year. New initiatives as the Cypriot Dry Stone Wall Exhibition at the Architecture Biennale in Venice as well as the Creative Island program involving 7 islands of the Mediterranean will give us insights and material to publish here in our Journal.

For the Art Journal we will undertake a new initiative to gather Artistic Expressions from different countries, for example photos of historic landscapes compared to the present situation of the same landscape.

For JOTL, the Journal of Terraced Landscapes, it will require a longer process as we follow the principle of double blind peer review. In our ITLA newsletter we will inform about the available scientific papers and the forthcoming issues.

Raimund Rodewald (Switzerland)

(born 1959 in Schaffhausen) holds a doctorate in biology and has been managing director of the Swiss Landscape Conservation Foundation (SL) in Bern since 1992. In 2008 he received an honorary doctorate from the Faculty of Law at the University of Basel. Thanks to his expert activities in numerous commissions and working groups, his great experience in conflict resolution processes and his lively publication activity, Raimund Rodewald has led landscape protection to become a widely recognised topic in Switzerland. He is a guest lecturer in landscape aesthetics at the ETH Zurich.

Traditional irrigation: A new Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity

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ABSTRACT

After dry stone walls, another infrastructure of terraced landscapes is in the focus of UNESCO: The submission titled “Traditional Irrigation: Knowledge, Technique, and Organization,” representing seven countries, was presented in March 2022 for consideration on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. On December 5, 2023, this cultural element was officially inscribed on the list, recognizing its importance in preserving traditional irrigation practices. The UNESCO Committee had already inscribed “Art of dry-stone walling, knowledge and techniques” on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity on 28 November 2018.

KEYWORDS

traditional irrigation, UNESCO, intangible cultural heritage, terraced landscapes

Introduction

On 30 March 2022, the application “Traditional Irrigation in Europe: Knowledge, Technique and Organization” was submitted to UNESCO for inclusion in the “Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity”. Austria took the lead in preparing the application together with Belgium, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and Switzerland. UNESCO evaluates the candidature in a procedure lasting several months. In Switzerland, the Wässermatten Oberaargau and the slope irrigation landscape of the Sonnenberge in the Upper Valais as well as five other water cooperatives in the Valais are involved. Some of these Suonen are also used today to irrigate vine terraces, however mostly in a technically modified way. The application was successful: On 5 December 2023 the UNESCO committee inscribed the Traditional Irrigation on the Representative List.

Traditional irrigation is a type of agricultural irrigation that relies on gravity and manually constructed structures such as channels and ditches to conduct water to the meadows, vines or gardens. Specific sets of rules and communal forms of organisation exist for watering.

Switzerland was the inspiration for the idea of a European candidature of traditional irrigation for the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. A programme advisory board led by Prof. Christian Leibundgut and the Swiss Foundation for Landscape Conservation (SL-FP) had been preparing this candidature since 2013. The aim is to make the knowledge, cultural significance and social practices associated with irrigation visible internationally as well. The typical cooperative organisation around irrigation, the preservation and transfer of knowledge and the associated techniques can only take place with the cooperation of all those involved. Above all, international exchange and the cooperation that goes with it are important strategies for contributing to the preservation of this intangible cultural heritage.

Traditional irrigation - a thousand-year-old tradition in Europe that is now under threat

Today, traditional irrigation, as the lowland irrigation or hillside irrigation, is threatened with

abandonment. In many places, technical irrigation systems have caused the disappearance of the tradition of irrigation of meadows, vines and gardens. Nevertheless, great efforts are visible internationally to preserve or reactivate this culture, which is up to a thousand years old. Climate adaptation and biodiversity promotion, but also social integration are new important functions of traditional irrigation techniques. In Switzerland, rescue operations for traditional irrigation have been successfully carried out since 1970 in the 108 ha large Wässermatten in Oberaargau and since the mid-1980s in Valais. Today, around 160 people are concretely involved in irrigation in the Oberaargau, and on the Upper Valais (Sonnenberge) there are several hundred people in the municipalities of Ausserberg and Baltschieder, as well as in the approximately 30 water cooperatives in the municipality of Naters. In addition, there are five other cooperatives listed in the UNESCO candidature: the Suone Eggeri in Grächen, the Grand Bisse de Lens, the Grand Bisse d'Ayent, the Bisse du Trient and the Bisse Vieux de Nendaz.

Intangible cultural heritage and UNESCO - protecting and documenting regional traditions and local knowledge

In addition to the UNESCO World Heritage Convention, the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage was launched by UNESCO in 2003. This placed the focus on people's traditional knowledge and their use of local resources and conditions, and gave international attention to the diverse living traditions. Traditional irrigation as a millennium-old knowledge makes an important contribution to sustainable development and the management of regional resources and promotes cohesion within the community. For example, through its contribution to groundwater accumulation, the practice helps mitigate flood risks, as well as the impacts of climate change at the local level (SDG 13 Climate Change Mitigation). The channels associated with irrigation (Waale¹, Suonen, Bisses) also contribute positively to the conservation and enhancement of local biodiversity (SDG 15 Life on Land).

Traditional irrigation is still a cooperative, sustainable, energy-independent and biodiversity-oriented solution for water supply in agriculture. It is of great importance for the practitioners themselves as well as for the wider society and the environment.

The important local significance attributed to traditional irrigation has already been recognised by the inscription of the practice on the “National Lists of Intangible Cultural Heritage” in all seven countries involved. A joint effort was undertaken to add this tradition to the international list, aiming to raise awareness of this important cultural element on a broader scale. The Intergovernmental Committee of the Conference of the Parties, which convenes annually, cast the final vote on the inclusion of Traditional Irrigation in Europe during its 18th session in December 2023.

Spectacular water worlds around the vine terraces of the Valais

Agricultural use on slopes in the semi-arid regions of the inner and Rhaetian Alps, in the Valais, in parts of Ticino and Grisons, such as in the Val Müstair and the Engadine, basically requires two things: firstly, soil, and secondly, water, whereby the latter was needed less for the rather undemanding cultivation of crops and more for gardens, meadows and

Figure 1. Bisse de Clavau are still used today to irrigate vines on the terraced landscapes of central Valais.

pastures. Just as the soil had to be brought in for the terracing of the fields, or at least brought up again after alluvial deposits, the water also had to be brought in via artificially constructed channels. These channels, called Suonen, Wasserleiten or Bisses in the Valais, were also poetically called “holy waters” because of their vital function - based on Jakob Christoph Heer’s novel “An heiligen Wassern” (1898).

Since there was a lack of water on the sunny, primarily south-facing slopes due to the lack of springs, it was diverted from the glacial streams by means of an ingenious canal system and transported in open, often kilometer-long channels and ditches at an equal gradient to the villages and meadows. There it could be used according to certain rules. The water rights were recorded in documents, which today are among the oldest written documents of many Valais communities. As a rule, construction and maintenance were the responsibility of private cooperative bodies made up of families who depended on the irrigation and also negotiated the maintenance obligations among themselves. The strictly

Figure 2. Bisse de Lentine (near Sion) are still used today to irrigate vines on the terraced landscapes of central Valais.

Figure 3. *Ancient vine irrigation* (©Collection Musée valaisanne de la Vigne et du Vin).

regulated water rights assigned specific watering times to each user and were ordered in a “Wasserkehr” (the rotation of irrigation). The maintenance of the water channels was assigned to selected individuals. The water channels are therefore part of an ancient anthropogenic landscape design. Written testimonies from the Valais become frequent since the 13th century. They form water worlds in the midst of dry mountain slopes that are historical but still relevant today and will become more important again in the future due to climate change.

Several impressive water channels supplied the terraced vineyards around Sion. They diverted water from the Liène valley (Bisse de Clavau, dating from around 1450 (Figure 1)) or from the Sionne valley (Bisse de Lentine, built in 1862 (Figure 2)). The vineyards around Sierre also had to be irrigated with water channels. Victor Pulliat mentions

the saying: “Pas de Bis, pas de vigne” (No Bisse, no vine) in 1885. The water there was channelled over the broken schist (“brisées”) that covered the vineyard floor. Thanks to the schist, which is rich in potassium and phosphate, this also caused a certain natural fertilisation. Even today, a few winegrowers still practice this traditional vine irrigation out of conviction.

With the introduction of technical sprinkler systems in 1930 and the corresponding state subsidies, the traditional practice of irrigating vines and meadows (Figure 3) gradually disappeared. Many exposed channels that could only be maintained with great effort were laid in tunnels, enclosed in concrete shells or completely piped. The irrigation systems with hydrants and pumping systems still often use the water from the Suonen. In the vineyards in particular, they were often equipped with ugly concrete installations, pressure pipelines and all kinds of tubes. The former charm of the water channels has completely put aside. Thus wrote Walter Schmid in 1955: “Many of the conduits have lost their romance in recent years because, in the course of their modernisation, the engineers have replaced the wildest passages on the rock walls with tunnel constructions and the wooden channels with bare cement pipes. The old Suonen are increasingly going this way, and on this occasion one cannot avoid the question of whether one day, when technology has modernised the picturesque old installations step by step with the sobriety proper to our time, a voice might not be raised in the federal lands that feels obliged to demand the protection of the old-venerable ‘Bisses’ that require much work, effort and care” (Walter Schmid 1955. *Komm mit mir ins Wallis, Bern*). This voice has now become loud.

Louis Courthion had already pointed out the tourist value of the Suonen in 1920. Numerous books and the artistically outstanding photographic documentation of the folklore culture and landscapes of the Valais from the end of the 19th century contributed to raising awareness. Films also were important, like “An heiligen Wassern” (1960) and “Wasserwosser - Die Waale”, a film from the Vinschgau Valley at the beginning of the 1980s.

Since that time, there has been a real rediscovery of the Valais’ channels. In 1982, the

organisation Switzerland Tourism proclaimed the “Year of the Suonen/Bisses” for the Valais. When a hydroelectric power plant was planned for the Baltschiederbach, the fate of the five remaining Suonen in the valley seemed sealed. With a protection agreement between the Swiss Foundation for Landscape Conservation (SL-FP) and the four valley municipalities, the end of the centuries-old irrigation system was prevented in 1986.

Although today there are federal and cantonal subsidies for the maintenance of the open water channels and their paths, these are often not enough, so that institutions such as the SL-FP and the Swiss Landscape Fund have to help. Thanks to them, numerous restoration projects could be realised. Various publications and tourist writings promoted public awareness. In 2010, a candidacy for UNESCO was discussed for the first time at an international colloquium on the water channels in Sion. In 2022, the candidacy has now been submitted with hopefully a positive outcome. In September 2022, an international center for traditional irrigation (IZTB) was established in St. Urban, Switzerland, with the goal of fostering knowledge exchange and networking in this field. The center was founded by Prof. Christian Leibundgut, widely regarded as Europe’s leading expert on traditional irrigation. Sadly, Prof. Leibundgut passed away in December 2023.

Until March 2026, the recently inscribed UNESCO element will be expanded to include additional interested countries, such as France, Greece, Spain, and Portugal.

The open water channels and the traditional irrigation with their centuries-old history are also indispensable for tourism, climate adaptation and biodiversity in the future. For the maintenance of the terraced landscapes, they will certainly gain more importance in the future, because both types of traditional landscapes of UNESCO unique value depend on communities of people who act together as care-takers for a cultural heritage of Humanity which reflects specially in these dark times a ray of light for peace..

Endnotes

1. Waale is the used term for water channels in North and South Tyrol; Suonen is used in the German part and Bisses in the French part of the Valais

Further reading

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<https://ich.unesco.org/en/18com>

<https://www.iztb.org/index.php/de/?view=article&id=54:eintrag-unesco&catid=53>

Sonia Schmid (Italy)

was born in Trento, Italy, and lives in Rovereto where she works in a hospital as a biomedical laboratory technician. She is part of La Pimpinella association, whose mission is to protect the agricultural biodiversity of the Trentino region.

She is attentive to the agrarian landscape where she walks slowly observing and collecting evidence. She is self-taught in method and writing. On the occasion of the Terraced Landscape Festival organized by the Sassi e non solo association, she exhibited the texts of some short stories about place names related to the stones of the Terragnolo valley.

The terraced landscape of the Terragnolo Valley

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ABSTRACT

The steep terraced side of the Terragnolo valley (Trentino, Italy) is today almost completely reforested. Depopulation, which began with First World War, resulted in the abandonment of cultivation of terraced fields. By traversing the territory on foot, it is possible to discover and recognize its features and concretely visualize the kilometer-long development of the ancient terracing walls with their ecosystems. Walking among terraces, at first glance made uniform by forest, agricultural and manufacturing ruins are revealed. The toponymy of places and oral testimonies help to understand the ancient and recent past of the territory and the new ways of inhabiting the valley. The International Terraced Landscape Festival and Competition, organized by Sassi e non solo and held in the Terragnolo Valley since 2017, aims to promote the ancient construction technique, inscribed in 2018 on the UNESCO's Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity.

KEYWORDS

terraced landscape, toponymy, path, biodiversity, festival

presents a continuous succession of rises and small valleys. The Leno di Terragnolo, once joined to the branch of the same name that descends from Vallarsa near the town of Rovereto, crosses it and then flows into the river Adige.

Stretched in a semicircle between the Colsanto Pasubio massif (2232 m.a.s.l.) and the Maggio (1853 m.a.s.l.) and Finonchio (1603 m.a.s.l.) mountains, it is exposed in such a way that one of its slopes is sunlit, while the other remains mostly in the shade (Figure 2). The morphological structure of the valley, characterised by the karstic erosion of its sedimentary rocks with a calcareous or dolomitic composition, has characterised its socio-historical evolution, so that the two slopes have taken on very different landscape characteristics: the orographic right is largely supported by terracing structures, while the left, furrowed by deep avalanches, is covered by woodland.

Christian Schneller, a linguist professor at the end of the 19th century, wrote, searching for the origin of the name Terragnolo (Schneller, 1890, p.167): *Thal der kleinen Ebenen* (The Valley of the small plateaus), a note of sweetness to define a rugged valley, which has

Figure 2. *The two sides of the Terragnolo valley (photo by Renato Stedile).*

Figure 3. The landscape of toil: terracing near Valduga (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 4. Development of terracing at the hamlet of Campi (photo by Renato Stedile)

always been linked to the nearby town of Rovereto by trade and small trades. The average slope of the cultivable areas is the highest in the entire southern Trentino (OP, 2017) and is about 23°; 78% of these areas are poorly accessible. These are factors that still today, together with land fragmentation, condition the return to cultivation of the land: the small, even tiny terraces, small patches of land just a few square metres in size, created by stealing land from the slope, are the identity character of the valley, whose landscape is defined as the landscape of toil (Figure 3).

Today, the municipality of Terragnolo has about seven hundred residents divided into thirty-three hamlets, thirty of which are located on the sunny side, some most dedicated to cultivation¹, while only three remain on the shaded side, namely Geroli, Pinterreno and Ghesteri, the latter being completely uninhabited.

2. HISTORY

The laborious work of clearing, tilling and levelling the rough slopes began around the year 1200, by specialised labourers of Bavarian Tyrolean origin (Cimbri), the so-called *roncadores* (Sarzo, 2006; Valduga, 2015). Hundreds of unknown landscape architects remained anonymous, who colonised the valley mixing with the sparse local population, handing down together knowledge and artefacts. Artefacts made to last as long as possible. Of the presence in Terragnolo of this population, traces remain even today in many dialect words, but above all in the very rich local toponymy. It is estimated that in the entire valley about three hundred linear kilometres of retaining structures were raised, with precision and skill, to an average height of 757 metres (Figure 4). The period of maximum inhabited development occurred at the beginning of the nineteenth century, when the population reached the number of about three thousand inhabitants. Subsequently, following the events of the First World War, which saw Terragnolo as a borderland and therefore the site of terrible battles between the Italian and Austro-Hungarian armies, the slow and inexorable depopulation of the territory began, where the subsistence economy could no longer guarantee a future. The identity traits of this valley are well represented in the

Figure 5. Mule track in the valley of Terragnolo (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 6. Ancient path between the hamlet of Perini and the hamlet of Valgrande (photo by Renato Stedile)

municipal coat of arms in which an axe and a spade stand out as a reminder of the work of generations of *roncadores* and a migratory bird resting on the water, a symbol of the migratory destiny of so much of the population.

From each of the thirty-three hamlets departed paths, mule tracks (Figure 5) or cart tracks that connected them one to the other, called *pontere* when they were very steep (the best known is the one that climbed steeply from Valgrande to Scottini); and those *stradei*, that is, little roads, that once made the terraced cultivated fields accessible right down to the houses². Many of these small paths that innervated the terraced fields and climbed up from the stream to the woods and meadows for grazing or mowing have unfortunately fallen into disuse and/or been interrupted, but are an essential part of Terragnolo's cultural landscape. Many others can only be travelled (Figure 6) on foot: a limitation or an opportunity?

3. TOPONYMY

Every place, no matter how small, but also the small valleys and gullies known as *tovi*, rocks, stony paths, woods, caves, meadows, fields, was experienced and made familiar with the aid of a name, which represented a sort of address, so much so that the place names in the Terragnolo valley number more than one thousand five hundred and many are of Cimbrian origin (see: <https://www.cultura.trentino.it/Patrimonio-on-line/Dizionario-toponomastico-trentino/>).

It is interesting to cite some of them, both Cimbrian and Latin, relating to terracing: *Fratte* for clearing the land down to ground level, *Laite* when the terrain was particularly sloping, *Banche* where timber was piled up, *Langhem*, *Langaraut*, *Langarnechele* or *Vaneze* to describe long plateaus, *Vigrive* for unproductive land; *Lambre* were the stony ground, *Raito*, *Raut*, *Raitle*, *Prechele* the cleared land. Higher up, where the terraced soil yielded to the rising mountain slopes and rocks, in the toponymy we find *Rive* and *Rivazzi* to indicate mountain ridges, *Avalesco*, *Avanterlin* if they were grassy verges; and again *Albi*,

Figure 7. *Sas dei morti on the path between the hamlet of Fontanelle and the hamlet of Valduga (photo by Renato Stedile)*

Pozze, Albiot, Aqua, Fontanei to indicate the presence of water; *Echile* the rises; *Vignai* and *Pomare* the land cultivated with vines or apple trees respectively; *Carnavecherle* indicated a field cultivated with wheat, *Ghertarle* small vegetable gardens; *Brol, Campi, Campetti, Campigoj* were large and small fields; *Plezzo, Plezzle* the clearings. There were also flat points for loading hay and timber, the *Cargaore*, and those for resting, known as *Polsaore*.

The valley's inhabitants also relied on large stones to map the territory by sharing names and locations: Terragnolo, rather than being made of a lot of earth, is made of many stones, eroded, broken and turned over, that is, *Marochi* large and small. This is well known by the rain, which has always, rushing down the valley, sought them out and seduced them one by one... or in small and large landslips *Slavine, slavinete, slavinoni*. Thus, names have been given to the ledges that crown the valley; then to the many overlapping banks of rock, the

Scafe, to the rock steps, to the rock outcrops, to the big rocks, to the landslide rocks, to the rock faces. Of some boulders, some anecdotes are known, even linked to ancient Cimbrian traditions, as in the case of the one called *Popolo mio* (My little boy), which watches over the village of Zoreri from on high; of others, the particularity of the shape remains in the name, such as that of the *Sas³ Quadro* (square sas), the *Sas Lonch* (Long sas), the *Lasto*; or the funny curiosity for the *Sas dei sghiti* (Bird droppings sas), or the reference to the bear for the *Sas de la Perlum* (Perlum sas); the engraving caused by the passage of carts betrays the history of the *Sas del Caret* (Cart sas); or the name indicated the function in the case of the *Sas del Fil* from which a cableway departed and the *Sas dei morti* (Dead Sas) (Figure 7) on which the litter of the deceased carried on the shoulders of the cemetery of San Nicolò at the bottom of the valley was placed; or indicated the nickname of the family to which the boundary of the wood belonged, as for the *Sas del Cuiar*; or the dark colour of the rocky outcrop of the *Sas negro* (Dark sas).

4. YESTERDAY'S AND TODAY LANDSCAPE

Those rare black and white military photographs from the early 20th century are impressive, or those from the 1930s where a practically bare valley, devoid of forest vegetation, was immortalised. A stage traversed by the infinite clear lines of the retaining structures: linear, interrupted, intertwined, denser where there are high slopes, more rarefied where the slope decreases a little. At present, they are for the most part rendered invisible by the homogenising advance of the forest, which was once kept at a proper distance from the terracing, and which has now taken revenge over more than eighty per cent of the meadows and fields. For this reason, one can only get a good idea of the succession of terraces (Figure 8) by crossing the land on foot, paying attention to what the green blanket of the forest conceals. One passes by walls sometimes clawed by ivy, which gets into the cracks and melts into the ashlar so much so that one ends up not being able to tell which one is carrying and which one is clinging on.

Figure 8. Succession of terraces on the edge of the forest above the hamlet of Zoreri at an altitude of 900 m.a.s.l. (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 9. Cabbage cultivation continues today in the small fields at the hamlet of Pedrazzi (photo by Renato Stedile)

5. AGRICULTURE IN THE PAST

The crops of yesteryear, until the mid-20th century, were those of a self-sustenance economy, spread over a dry land, poor in nutrients, where the manure, *la grassa* was brought to the fields using the *fil*, small cableways where possible, or, by the women, over their shoulders, even relaying between them. For this purpose, the so-called *béne* were used, sturdy baskets (and obviously permeable to sewage...) woven from the flexible branches of the hazel tree, the size of which could vary depending on the function performed, if the contents to be transported were soil, fertiliser, vegetables, hay, wood, coal: *Gh'era le bene da slita e quele da carga* - There were sled baskets and cargo baskets (Ronz C.) “*Ah, se ne ho fat su de béne sti anni coi noselèri*” – Ah, how many baskets I built with halz branches (Peterlini F.); “*En primavera ne tocheva portar su con la zivera la tera che rudoleva zo in inverno*” – In the spring we had to carry high the earth that rolled down in winter using a stretcher (Zencher M.) can still be heard today from the elderly, who keep those daily tribulations etched in their memories.

Together with the exploitation of the forest, from logging to the cooking of coal and lime, to the domestic rearing of a few cows, pigs, goats and rabbits, the multi-crop horticulture and fruit-growing ensured, albeit meagrely, family survival. Wheat, barley, rye, cabbage (Figure 9), potatoes and turnips were also cultivated and sold in exchange for *zaldo*, i.e. corn for cooking polenta, which was the staple food of the population until the 1950s.⁴

The area planted with vines, the so-called *Vignai*, was mainly that of the bottom of the valley near San Nicolò, Fontanelle, and that descending from Serrada towards Valduga. “*Under each vineyard, next to the retaining wall, a strip of buckwheat was sown*” (Ronz C.). “*At the bottom of every arbour on the path is the bigoncia (conzal), which, when it is full, is carried on the shoulders across the steep paths and up the steps to the road, where the vats (brentoni) are*” (Mattevi, 1957 p.57). Even today, those few who still tend the small family vineyards carry the grapes uphill in buckets.

The possibility of irrigation used to determine crop yields. Some terraced fields just upstream of the Leno stream were devoted to the cultivation of beans, precisely because

of the easy access to water. Two toponyms identifying the small fields below Valduga are curious and significant: *Cucagna* the first (Cuccagna: fabulous country, without worries, where abundance is the norm), *Merica* the second (America, the land of dreams, of the coveted well-being to which many desperately emigrated). A few rare tobacco plants were cultivated furtively in the higher fields, hidden among the *rame dei fasoi*, i.e. branches to make runnerbeans grow (Potrich. P.).

Cherry, apple and pear trees prevailed on the higher terraces. Many still remain, often as relics among brambles, crushed by ivy and dried up to hide a fruit biodiversity that is not entirely lost, and perhaps to be revalued. Like the quality of Villari apples, the mizi peri, the one-lire pear trees, ripening from a solitary plant in a field below Castello, frequented mainly by chamois. “*Pear trees so large that they could be sold for a lira each*” (Zencher G). With apples “The farmers used to make cider for family use, and the Gasperi, who at Scottini, a thousand metres above sea level, cultivated hops, produced their own beer until the 1950s” (Valduga L.). A few years ago, a young man started growing hops again: “*The inflorescences are used to make beer, but the tender, delicate shoots are excellent to eat*” (Scrinzi R.).

A local grape variety, called *Nera dei Baisi* to refer to the hamlet where there was only one vineyard left, was instead saved from extinction thanks to the project of a Vallagarina⁵ winery.

On the small plains, there was no lack of mulberry trees, the leaves of which had been used since the end of the 1600s to feed silkworms, the *cavalieri*, bred on special reed trellises, the *arele*: together with the *slite* (cargo sleds), some still protrude from the attics, *le teze*, of the oldest dwellings in Terragnolo, since silkworm cultivation, especially from the early 1800s (Cobelli, 1872) and up to the mid-1950s, contributed to the family income. “*Sul ciglio del muro gh'era i gelsi, drio i fasoi, poi le patate o altri ortaggi, zo e zo fim al Lem*” - On the edge of the wall were the mulberries, behinds the beans, then the potatoes and other vegetables, down and down to the Leno (Ronz C.). Then came the First World War to devastate the territory: “*With the military order of a sudden displacement, there were those who, out of*

desperation and with a loving gesture, freed all the silkworms under mulberry trees” (Valduga L.) In the heart of the hamlet of Perini, a beautiful old plant welcomes visitors, in Baisi others, periodically pruned, look out over the valley, but if you look closely, you can still find them, albeit now rare, among the houses and in the fields of almost all the hamlets of Terragnolo. On the paths between the terraced fields in springtime, the yellow cornel blossoms, and at the end of summer, its red berries offer both sight and taste. A hard wood its, once used to make the handles of axes, hammers, mallets.

A lot of *formentom*, that is buckwheat, was sown as a second crop, after potatoes or grasses, i.e. wheat, rye, and barley. Not a cereal but a polygonaceous plant, whose food use is, however, similar to that of grasses, which is well adapted to growing on the leanest soils. Visual impressions of the terraced landscape run through those who remember it all being cultivated, comparing it to a garden: “*Observed from above, during flowering, the spectacle of the white patches of earth (Figure 10) juxtaposed with the colours of the other crops in fields and fields, one next to the other, was moving*” (Zencher P.). The *formentom*, having reached maturity, was harvested by uprooting it by hand or cutting it off at the base with the *zesla* (sickle) or by hand, above all and again by women, and left to dry and darken in the field, gathered into characteristic small sheaves (Figure 11) known as *donéte*, small women, with a red skirt given by the colour of the stalks. “*Ghe se vol terem magro per farlo madurar, altrimenti el mateza*” (Gerola E.), “*el stramazza*” (Valduga L.): it must be sown on thin soil for it to ripen, otherwise it bends.

With black buckwheat flour, *polenta mora*, dark, was cooked; or a sort of thin, traditional alpine bread was prepared, different from family to family, called *fanzelto*, by mixing together water, salt and flour to form a dense dough and frying it in an iron pan with lard, in the shape of a pancake. The recipe is now a “DeCo”⁶.

This irreverent inscription is curious: “They also say (the people of Rovereto) that the fields are so steep that the valley dwellers stick the manure to the ground with a mistletoe to make it stick to them, and to sow the beech trees, they shoot them with a revolver, and finally, so that the eggs don’t run into the stream, they stick a bag on the chickens” (Ferrari, 1934 p. 4).

Figure 10. Buckwheat in bloom at the hamlet of Campi (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 11. Small sheaves of buckwheat harvested by hand (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 12. Terragnolo women returning to the valley from Rovereto (1901) (Place: Tartarotti Rovereto Public Library)

6. WOMEN TRADE AND TERRAGNOLE PATH

In the not-too-distant past, that is, up until the end of the 1950s - those who can bear direct witness to this are still alive -, it was the women (the Terragnole) who took care of the small trades from which they drew a meagre income, very important for the family economy. Leaving before dawn by the dim light of oil lamps, they would walk down to Rovereto, to the town, *coi rufi ai pei* (jute or rag shoes on their feet) (Zencher M.) and the *scarpeloti*, (crampons) in winter, carrying on their shoulders, hanging from hooks on a curved wood called *zerla*, the *raminei* milk canisters, baskets with butter, cheese, fruit depending on the season, mushrooms, mountain flowers (cyclamens, lilies of the valley, gentians, negritella and rhododendrons), legumes and even bundles of wood, pine cones to light the fire, even *la zendro per far la lissia* (Stedile M.), ash to prepare lye: all to make some small profit, or to exchange their produce for maize flour (Stedile, 2009). In some cases, between the outward and return journeys (Figure 12), the kilometres travelled on foot each day were between twenty and thirty, first downhill and then, finally, uphill, to look after family and animals. This path, today very popular, twelve kilometres long, restored in 2009 and enriched since 2013 with six illustrative notice boards describing the peculiarities of the area, was named Sentiero delle Terragnole (Terragnole Path), in memory of their labours.

7. BUILDING TECHNIQUES

Some elderly people from Terragnolo still testify to the technique of building, but above all repairing walls, which was not usually a solitary task, but done at least in pairs using *liovera* and *leverim*, *mazot* and *sgiandim*, *martelina*, *pic* and *bail*, *barele e slite de legn per portar i sasi*⁷.

Water in the terraces was, and is, the great absentee. Every source, even the smallest, was structured and used: the name *fonte del Piocio*⁸ (a small one with a low but constant inflow) speaks volumes. It was collected in special wells, tanks, fountains. Walking along the paths

or crossing the bush, one still comes across these artefacts placed under the long walls: the oldest ones are made of stone, the most recent ones of cement, and in any case, those built after 1940, which sometimes still glow blue from the verdigris and slaked lime dissolved in them to be sprayed on the vines. "... these terraces that climb stubbornly by the dozens from the stream down to below the woods, not as far as there is economic convenience, but as far as the law of gravity allows the masonry and the earth to remain standing, not for years but at least until the end of the season." (Ferrari, 1934 p.13).

8. PRESENT ACTIVITIES

8.1. Exploring terraced landscapes

To walk now in the Terragnolo valley (Schmid, 2020) is to follow, in silence, dozens of paths branching out mainly through the bush, starting from two main arterial roads that descend to Rovereto town. The network of minor paths is almost entirely among the dishevelled terraced landscape, unfortunately in inevitable decline, largely abandoned but nevertheless rich in evidence of the exploitation of the forest - for example the disused overhanging wires -, agricultural activity, milling and smelting.

In summer, listening to the shrill, incessant chirping of cicadas where the exposure is sunny, one can pause to discover the rich, walled flora (Stedile, Sarzo, 2016), which in ancient times was also used in traditional medicine, and be surprised by the wildflowers or the coming and going of a titmouse that has nested in a cavity between the ashlar. The shady walls, those close to the stream, are instead cloaked in thick layers of damp mosses (Figure 13) and ferns, inhabited by snails and salamanders that are not difficult to encounter on rainy days.

In winter, on the other hand, when the valley lays bare its stone skeleton, it is certainly easier to notice the great work of domestication of the mountain territory and to identify not only the network of dry-stone walls, high, low, double-sided, pitched, with or without access steps, built overhanging or inside the walls themselves, but also all the other rural

Figure 13. Mosses growing among the stones of wet walls on the path up from the Leno stream to the hamlet of Gbesteri (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 14. Calchera ruin at the hamlet of Valgrande (photo by Renato Stedile)

architecture functional to it. Some seventy ruins of old *casote ai vignai* and *baitei* are recorded in a precious volume by Luigi Valduga, a passionate historian of Terragnolo, but these are joined by those of sawmills, mills, forges, about eighty *calchere* (Figure 14) - furnaces to produce lime, and the now practically invisible traces of about sixty charcoal kilns (Valduga, 2010). It is also possible to come across the remains of military artefacts dating back to the First World War: walls supporting cableways, ruins of barracks, small fountains for supplying water to the troops. A stratification of history to be read: a rusty sickle, a dented enamelled cup, a bent fork, a shrapnel may jump out from the stones of the walls; in the old ruins, a barrel, a wooden rake, skeins of wire recovered from disused vineyards, metal buckets abandoned before saying goodbye, a hand-beaten nail slowly slipping out of a door, while a vine shoot (Figure 15) looks for another opportunity.

It is therefore necessary to walk in order to observe the many stones: hundreds of thousands of them wedged together in terracing walls; those superimposed in the elementary geometries of buildings and in the *calchere*; those chamfered to make the pavement of paths and in which one often notices the grooves cut by the skids of heavy sledges; those skilfully worked to become artefacts such as *albi* drinking troughs in which wild amphibians now breed, millstones and pestles, called *pile*, which are not infrequently found displayed with affection in front of houses. Boundary stones, tombstones, even dating back to the 1600s, testify to the transit along the ancient and dangerous paths. Some wounded scenes cannot be missed, large stone quarries, from which pearl-grey marble was extracted up to seventy years ago. “*But each family had its own small stone quarry*” (Zencher G.). The stones are reduced, even in the place names, into smaller and smaller pieces: stones accumulated in the *marogne e marognette*, i.e. in the destonerments, or crumbled in the *gère*. Pebbles, which become grains in the gully known as *La riso* or which finally pulverise and knead into clay, the so-called *lea*, once used to work the roof tiles by hand.

A few small fields, albeit uncultivated, and a few paths in the valley are periodically cleared of brush at their own expense by individuals or groups of volunteers: a struggle to stem the wood and the advance of brambles repaid by the beauty of the geometry of the landscape. Certainly, every small individual action, the care of the small and the possible, is useful in

Figure 15. An abandoned vine climbs a ruin locality Loch at the hamlet of Pedrazzi (photo by Sonia Schmid)

adding aesthetic value to the old walls of the valley. For years, the Proloco of the hamlet of Zoreri has been giving a tangible example of cooperation in the restoration of historical pathways, cleaning up some terraces, reconstructing footbridges on the Leno stream.

8.2. Cultivation of food from autochthonous seeds

A few years ago, a project was started in some terraced fields to reintroduce the voluntary and collective cultivation of buckwheat. The seed is an autochthonous one, an ecotype from Terragnolo, as certified by the typification carried out by the University of Padua, to which the Associazione la Pimpinella (an association that deals with the recovery, rescue and conservation of the horticultural and fruit-growing heritage of the Trentino valleys) had handed over some seeds entrusted to it by a historical farmer of the valley, Francesco “Franz” Potrich. “Eating is an agricultural act”, wrote W. Berry, an American poet, farmer and environmentalist (Berry, 2015): in autumn, before the harvest, a community walk is organised among the ‘formentom’ fields, an agro-cultural itinerary to discover or rediscover how much the agricultural territory and eating habits modify the landscape. This ambitious project has moreover evolved into the purchase of a community mill, inaugurated in the hamlet of Zoreri in 2022.

Beans, cabbage, potatoes, leeks, onions: these too are cultivated today in the vegetable gardens that climb the Terragnolo valley. And turnips, the seeds of which G. Peterlini and also saved and valorised by Pimpinella are another product that could be said to be the identity of this terraced valley, like certain types of climbing beans, the *fasoì da la rama*: “*Ghe se vol late alte almem tre metri, de frassem e coi speronzini en do tacarse per farli rampegar su ben, se no, i casca zo*” (Gerola E.), poles at least three metres high are needed for them to climb, made of ash wood, with small spurs to make them climb well, otherwise they fall. With one important difference from the past: with the return of the forest, the disturbing presence of ungulates that cross the fields down to below and houses, deer above all, roe deer and chamois, forces one to fence off every sown or cultivated place and this factor is a further disincentive to take up terraced fields again. As well as the presence of the wolf, which recently alarmed Leonardo G. who raises cattle (Figures 16, 17) and the passage of the bear destroyed some beehives a few years ago.

Figure 16. Leonardo's cows graze freely in the terraced fields near the hamlet of Campi (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 17. Goats graze at the entrance of the Cargaore trail near the hamlet of Zoreri (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 18. The restoration of the rural building "Maso Cesura" and the large terraces that have been cultivated again (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 19. The Cesura double side walls, leading to the Cesura farmstead (photo by Renato Stedile)

8.3. Buildings restoration

A recent and interesting restoration of a large rural building (Figure 18) and the wide terraces on which it stands is being consolidated at the *Mas della Cesura*. The *cesure* were formerly enclosed, fenced areas: in this case, precisely by large, double-sided dry-stone walls (Figure 19). An engineer, a lover of landscape and good food, has restored a large area that had remained uncultivated for decades, planting hedges, fruit trees of both new and local varieties; giving vigour to a large vegetable garden; sowing a field of buckwheat and planting hundreds of lavender plants, hosting a few bee hives: *“It’s great to have chamois and roe deer grazing in front of the doorway, but everything I want to produce, I have to protect by raising high fences! Including the young fruit trees that I must wrap in netting cylinders to save them from the bites of the deer that lean and stand up to over two metres”* (Dapor V.)

9. TERRACED LANDSCAPES FESTIVAL

Terragnolo is the ideal rural landscape, with its slopes and terraces of all sizes, for the annual Festival and international contest on the terraced landscape, organised since 2017 by the SASSI E NON SOLO⁹ association together with the Trentino Dry Stone School, which cultivates and passes on this type of non-polluting construction technique, knowledge of which is necessary for the restoration and maintenance of the terraced landscape. The Festival takes place in Geroli, which can be reached by travelling along the entire length of the valley and thus being able to see the entire extent of the Terragnolo territory and catch a glimpse of the terracing. In Geroli, large plots of rough meadows are still mowed, which in the spring display a spectacular flowering. It is a concrete and discreet festival, hosting national and international masters. It is not folklore, but a cooperative event, in which teams of expert dry-stone craftsmen compete from dawn to dusk in the reconstruction from scratch of a section of terracing wall without using any kind of binder, leaving in place not so much new retaining walls as small works of art and a long vision of the future of the middle lands forced to accept, after that of depopulation, also the challenge of ongoing climate change.

A further contribution of the Festival, its added value, is that of allowing an inexperienced public to see the construction and appreciate the artefact from its foundations to its crowning, listening to an ancient tapping: if in fact one understands the function of a wall built in dry stone, at first glance one does not perceive the soul, or rather, one does not see it. The sober and powerful soul remains hidden, rooted in the earth or among the stones, and is visible only on two occasions: if one is lucky, in the moment of the birth of the “little wall”, or more and more frequently, in the fields and woods, in the clean agony of the return of the pieces to the earth. Walls, too, are born bare and clean, then as they become more familiar, they grow fat with earth and colour. Therefore, if one does not really need to build a dry-stone wall from scratch, at the Festival in Terragnolo one has the opportunity to look at just where the soul of the walls sinks, which in a handful of hours, is assigned to them by the artisan builders, in their image and likeness (Figure 20). Then, only the façade remains to reveal the wall’s profound relationship with its “world within”, and in the Terragnolo valley, alongside the thousands of traditional historical façades, others are slowly being added, with new languages. One section of these walls has different stones, but all perfectly square, in another they are sought to be all of the same hue; there is the wall that does not care if one of its stones is rounder than the others, or less dressed or darker, less sharp or rougher. In some, the dimensions of the stones must absolutely resemble each other, which is not so important for others; the one in which the ashlar have been intentionally stacked all at an angle; in one there is no breathing space between stone and stone, in the other the spaces between the ashlar have been filled with thin flakes; the one with the flower in the centre, the one that cages a pot-bellied deer or holds an auspicious statuette; in the niche of the last of a cordonata a round *sas ru* has been laid. Some stones bear engraved symbols or alphabets identifying the culture of those who made them. Who knows how different the next wall will be, what language it will speak, while respecting the rules of art, harmony and intonation with the environment of Geroli. A young enrichment, both functional and aesthetic, for a valley with a history as ancient as that of Terragnolo and from which it would have everything to gain.

Figure 20. Some new dry stone walls built by the teams that participated in the editions of the Terraced Landscape Festival at the hamlet of Geroli (photo by Renato Stedile)

Figure 21. The beauty of the terraced landscape crossed by the Terragnole path near the hamlet of Perini, (photo by Renato Stedile)

10. CONCLUSION

Terragnolo's terraced landscape, of simple and unarmed beauty (Figure 21), would need constant maintenance for its redevelopment, even for tourism, which would in any case remain a niche, now that for years the sweat and forced steps of the population have been replaced by the slow and relaxed ones of hikers.

To the question of who then is Terragnolo's terraced landscape, one could perhaps answer: the landscape is in the eyes of all those who see it and in the hands of those who, in whatever capacity, transform it, paradoxically even without moving a finger.

Endnotes

- 1 San Nicolò, Fontanelle, Perini, Potrich, Valgrande, Valduga, Scottini, Pornal, Dieneri, Peltreteri, Pedrazzi Piazza - municipal seat, Dosso, Puechem, Rovri, Croce, Castello, Costa, Valle, Pergheri, Zencheri, Stedileri, Sega, Maureri, Camperi, Baisi, Soldati, Zoreri, Incapo, Campi.
- 2 These were once built close to each other and 'housed not only the residential function, but also the agricultural one, having spaces specifically intended for the first processing and preservation of the products of the fields' (Ganassini, 2011, p.46).
- 3 The dialect term "Sas" means stone.
- 4 "The basis of the diet is polenta, which between large and small is consumed on average three quarters of a kilogram per person per day and is all bought in town" (Ferrari,1934, p.19).
- 5 Southern valley of Trentino crossed by Adige river.
- 6 De.Co.: municipal denomination of origin
- 7 These are tools used to dig, split, move stones and earth.
- 8 Louse source.
- 9 <https://www.facebook.com/sassienonsolo>

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